

Replacement of Sulphonic Groups by Nitro Groups in Aromatic Amino-compounds.

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In a previous communication (Datta and Varma, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 2089) it has been shown that in a number of phenolic compounds, sulphonic groups could be easily replaced by nitro groups by means of nitrous gases and a number of nitro-phenolic compounds in a fair state of purity and in good yields were obtained by this method. It has been possible to extend this investigation further and we find that the replacement of sulphonic groups by nitro groups is a general reaction in the case of aromatic amino-compounds also. In this case not only the sulphonic groups are replaced by nitro groups but the amino group is at the same time diazotised and replaced by the hydroxyl group so that the final products of the reaction in this case also are nitro-phenolic compounds. The products are in this case also as in the previous one generally free from bye-products and as a rule more than one nitro-group enters into the benzene nucleus.

It is interesting to find that in the case of naphthylamine sulphonic acid, the replacement of the sulphonic group by the nitro group is not brought about, though the amino-group is diazotised and replaced by the hydroxyl-group and the compound is nitrated as well. Thus a nitro-naphthol sulphonic acid has been obtained from a solution in chloroform of naphthylamine sulphonic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sulphanilic Acid.—Sulphanilic acid (10 g.) was partly dissolved and partly suspended in water (100 c.c.) and nitrous gases (obtained from arsenous oxide and nitric acid) passed. The gases were completely absorbed at the outset. The sulphanilic acid in suspension gradually passed into solution and the colour of the solution changed to greenish. Minute bubbles of gases were observed to escape.

When no more of the gas was absorbed, the solution was evaporated on the water-bath to a viscous consistency. On allowing to cool the product solidified. It was separated from the mother-liquor and crystallised from alcohol. The crystals (90 g., m. p. 122°) were found to be 2 : 4 : 6-trinitro-phenol.

Aniline-disulphonic Acid.—Aniline-disulphonic acid (10 g.), partly dissolved and partly suspended in water, was subjected to the action of nitrous gases until no more gases were absorbed. The reacting mixture was concentrated on the water-bath and allowed to cool and stand overnight. No solid separated. It was diluted and neutralised with powdered barium carbonate. The solution was filtered, boiled with animal charcoal, again filtered and the filtrate heated with the requisite quantity of sulphuric acid. The barium sulphate was removed by filtration. The filtrate was now concentrated on water-bath to a small volume. On allowing to cool, crystals (4 g.) of 2 : 4 : 6-trinitro-phenol were obtained.

m-Aniline Sulphonic Acid.—This sulphonic acid was prepared by sulphonating nitrobenzene and reducing the resulting nitrobenzene sulphonic acid by means of iron filings and sulphuric acid. *m*-Aniline sulphonic acid (5 g.) thus prepared was treated with nitrous gases for 30-40 minutes. The reacting solution was evaporated to about half the volume and allowed to cool and crystallise. Crystals (8 g., m. p. 150°) were obtained and found to be 2 : 5-dinitro-phenol.

p-Nitraniline Sulphonic Acid.—By sulphonating *p*-nitraniline, a sulphonic acid derivative was obtained. The solution of this product (5 g.) was subjected to the action of nitrous gases for about 20 minutes. Considerable frothing took place. The solution turned dark red. It was evaporated to half its volume, and the solid separated was crystallised from rectified spirit. Crystals of 2 : 4-dinitro-phenol, m. p. 112°, were obtained.

Dimethylaniline Sulphonic Acid.—By heating dimethylaniline (20 g.) with concentrated sulphuric acid at 180°-190° for three hours and a half, dimethylaniline sulphonic acid was obtained. The product so obtained was submitted to steam distillation to get rid of unchanged dimethylaniline. By concentrating the product a syrupy liquid was obtained. This was diluted with a small quantity of water and nitrous gases passed in a rapid stream for about 20 minutes. A copious yellow solid separated. It was removed, washed with water and crystallised from rectified spirit. Brownish

yellow shining crystals, m. p. 153° of 2:3:4-tri-nitrodimethyl amino-benzene were obtained. Yield 5.5 g.

o-Toluidine-5-sulphonic Acid.—This sulphonic acid was prepared and separated by the method of Gerver (*Annalen*, 1873, 169, 374). The solid product (10 g.) was dissolved in water and treated with nitrous gases until no more absorbed. The product obtained was separated and crystallised as usual. 3:5-Dinitro-*o*-cresol (5 g.) m. p. 86°, was obtained.

o-Toluidine-3:5-disulphonic Acid.—This was prepared by the method of Neville and Winther (*Ber.*, 1882, 15, 2992). The solid product was dissolved and treated in the same way as in the preceding case. 3:5-Dinitro-*o*-cresol (5 g.) from 8 g. of the disulphonic acid was obtained.

m-Toluidine Sulphonic Acid.—This was prepared by the method of Lorenz (*Annalen*, 1874, 172, 185) and treated with nitrous gases as before. On concentration and cooling a copious yellow precipitate was obtained. It was crystallised and found to be 2:4:6-trinitro-*m*-cresol (11.2 g.) from 10 g. of *m*-toluidine.

p-Toluidine-3-sulphonic Acid.—In this case if nitrous gases were passed for a long period, oxalic acid was the only product obtained. If however, care was taken in passing the gases for a few minutes only 3:5-di-nitro-*p*-cresol was obtained. In 10 g. of the sulphonic acid, fifteen minutes of passing the gases are enough to produce 3:5-di-nitro-*p*-cresol (3 g.). The yield decreases as the nitrous gases are passed for a longer period. In about 45 minutes, there is no trace of the dinitro-cresol, but on concentrating the solution and allowing it to cool in a desiccator, crystals of oxalic acid only are obtained.

p-Toluidine-3:5-disulphonic Acid.—No nitro-derivative could be obtained from this substance. Crystals of oxalic acid only were obtained.

m-Xylidine Sulphonic Acid.—This solid compound was dissolved in water and nitrous gases passed until no more absorbed. Some yellow solid separated during the process. On concentration on water-bath and cooling more yellow solid producted separated. It was crystallised and found to 5-nitro-1:3:4-xyleneol, m.p. 71-72°. (Found: N, 8.79. C, H, O, N requires N, 8.89 per cent.).

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